

Human-in-the-Loop Generation of Preservation Metadata for Research Dataset Segments

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Background

- Research datasets age fast: scripts, their environments, and even data specifications rot; bit-for-bit replay is brittle, whereas future migration requires context.
- Divide to conquer: Last year we argued that, even when related files overlap, it is effective to bundle the meaningful activities and artifacts that lead to a single primary outcome [1]—we call such a bundle a “research dataset segment.”
- Researchers hold the most accurate context about their own work, yet they are typically not specialists in long-term preservation or data dissemination.
- We adopt a human-in-the-loop YAML as SIP documentation that captures files, activities, rights, and related context. This helps collect the necessary context efficiently for each research dataset segment.

Core Idea

Take-Home Points

(1) One YAML → many standards, reproducibly.

From a single YAML, we emit METS 2.0, RO-Crate 1.1, and a TEI header via small, repeatable scripts—YAML as the single source of truth for rights/provenance and file references.

(Limitations: This YAML is a practical glue layer, not (yet) a preservation standard; we’ve validated on only few datasets, so the schema/content remain immature. Also, data that cannot be uploaded to ChatGPT (license/privacy constraints) limits how much assistance we can automate.)

(2) LLM-assisted metadata enrichment—with guardrails.

The assistant helps resolve IDs (e.g. ORCID, ROR), normalize licenses/agents, and draft file summaries, then we curate and persist results back to YAML for deterministic re-runs.

(Limitations: occasional mistakes—e.g., missed escaping of quotes in titles—so curator review is required. When ChatGPT asks too many follow-ups, users get fatigued.)

References and Attributions

[1] Kameda, A. et al. (2024). Exploring Preservation of Research Data and Its Context through Case Studies. iPRES 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13756258](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756258)

[2] Kameda, A., Ishii, K., Inoue, S., & Kokaze, N. (2025). Starting from Showing, Moving toward Sharing: Broadening TEI’s Reach. TEI 2025.

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- This poster template is from SIU Medical Library

What is Research Dataset “Segment”?

A segment is a meaningful process-bundle and its primary outcome carved out from a larger workflow. It is the unit we aim to preserve, cite, and reuse as a whole.

The primary outcome typically is one file (e.g., data.csv), though uniform files (e.g., 001.png – 008.png) can be treated as multiple primaries.

Why YAML?

- Human-in-the-loop SIP documentation. Captures what repositories miss: commands, context, rights, and rationale at submission time.
- LLM-friendly. Predictable keys, incremental filling, and machine-detectable TODO: stubs make guided collection practical.

Empirical note:

When we asked the model to produce both Markdown and METS 2.0 XML in one shot, the XML frequently drifted from the spec—wrong/default namespaces, illegal element placement (e.g., stray dmdSec, misused mdSec), and PREMIS wrapped in the wrong container.

We now collect everything in record.yaml and generate XML with deterministic scripts.

Example YAML (excerpt)

```
agents:
- id: a_kameda
  agent_type: person
  name: "Akihiro Kameda"
  identifiers:
  - scheme: orcid
    value: "0000-0002-5439-6456"
  affiliations:
  - name: "National Institutes for ..."
    identifiers:
    - scheme: ror
      value: "https://ror.org/040..."

activities:
- id: ev-2025-04-28-classification
  activity_type: "classification"
  datetime: "2025-04-28T00:00:00Z"
  agent_ids: ["ag-kameda"]
  used: ["f_merged"]
  generated: ["f_classified"]
  runinfo:
  argv: ["python", "chatgpt_classify..."]
  cwd: "classification/"
  env_keys: ["OPENAI_API_KEY"]

dataset:
  title:
  - value: "Correspondence between ..."
    language: en
  creators_ref: ["a_kameda", "a_ishii"]
  rights_ref: ["rs-ccby-40", "rs-mit"]

rights_sets:
- id: rs-ccby-40
  rights_uri: "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"
  rights_label: "CC BY 4.0"

files:
- id: f_primary
  path: "diff_and_corresp.csv"
  mimetype: "text/csv"
  title: "Comment-revision correspondence"
  rights_ids: ["rs-ccby-40"]
  additional_attributions: ["ag-moej"]
  primary: true
- id: f_classify_script
  path: "classification/chatgpt_classify.py"
  mimetype: "text/x-python"
  title: "LLM prompt & classification driver"
  rights_ids: ["rs-mit"]
```


Open
the GPT
assistant
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Discussion

- Scope: This work is about collecting & transforming metadata; we don’t implement a full OAIS pipeline.
- METS 2.0 by design: Although 1.x is common, 2.0 matched our “small, auditable bundles” approach—mdSec-only, rights/fixity/prov-first, and simpler to generate from record.yaml.
- PROV vs PREMIS: Describe workflow with PROV-like activities; record preservation events with PREMIS (creation; migration optional).
- Why JPCOAR (DIP): Aligns with CINI requirements; more practical than MODS for Japanese domestic distribution.
- Link each segment to the whole via stable project IDs. How should we describe and publish the linkage?